

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Ellikqal'a tumani misolida 2018–2024–yillar oralig'ida tuproq sho'rlanishi va iqlim omillarining o'zaro bog'liqligini tahlil qilish

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi Ellikqal'a tumanida 2018-2024-yillar oralig'ida tuproq sho'rlanishi va iqlim omillari o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik empirik ma'lumotlar asosida tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda NASA POWER va FAO WaPOR ma'lumotlar bazalaridan olingan oylik meteorologik (harorat, yog'in, bug'lanish, namlik) va gidroklimatik parametrlar, shuningdek, sho'rlanish (EC) qiymatlari ishlatilgan. Tahlil jarayonida ko'p manbali ma'lumotlar GIS muhitida integratsiya qilinib, regressiya modellari (MLR) yordamida iqlimiy determinantlarning sho'rlanish jarayoniga ta'sir darajasi aniqlangan. Natijalarga ko'ra, harorat (T) va bug'lanish (RET) sho'rlanishning asosiy ijobiy determinantlari sifatida, yog'in (PCP) esa manfiy determinant sifatida baholangan. 2018-2024-yillar oralig'ida suv balansining manfiy tendensiyasi ($RET > AETI$) kuzatilgan bo'lib, bu sho'rlanish jarayonining kuchayganini ko'rsatadi. GIS asosida qurilgan fazoviy xaritalar sho'rlanishning asosan g'arbiy va janubiy massivlarda kuchayganini ko'rsatadi.

Tadqiqot natijalari hududiy meliorativ boshqaruv, suv resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish va qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarini joylashtirish bo'yicha amaliy qarorlar qabul qilishda ilmiy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kirish. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 25-martdagi PQ-179-son qarori agrar sohada barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlash, suv va yer resurslaridan samarali foydalanish hamda sug'oriladigan yerlarning meliorativ holatini yaxshilashga qaratilgan muhim strategik hujjatdir. Ushbu qarorda ilmiy asoslangan agrotexnologiyalarni joriy etish, sug'orish tizimlarini raqamlashtirish va tuproq sho'rlanishini kamaytirish ustuvor vazifa sifatida belgilangan. Mazkur tadqiqot ana shu yo'nalishlarga mos holda, real kuzatuv ma'lumotlari asosida sho'rlanish va namlik jarayonlarini empirik tahlil qilishga qaratilgan.

Tuproq sho'rlanishi O'zbekistonning sug'oriladigan hududlarida qishloq xo'jaligi barqarorligini cheklovchi asosiy omillardan biri bo'lib, bu muammo Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi Ellikqal'a tumanida ayniqsa dolzarbdir. Hududning keskin kontinental iqlimi, kam yog'in va kuchli bug'lanish sharoitida suv balansining buzilishi grunt suvlarining sathi ko'tarilishiga va tuproqning ustki qatlamlarida tuzlar to'planishiga olib keladi. Shu sababli sho'rlanish jarayonining vaqtli dinamikasi va hududiy taqsimotini aniqlash muhim ilmiy-amaliy vazifa hisoblanadi.

So'nggi yillarda ushbu jarayonlarni modellashtirish bo'yicha xalqaro tadqiqotlar olib borilgan bo'lsa-da [1], ularning aksariyati nazariy yondashuvlarga asoslangan. Ushbu ish esa Ellikqal'a tumani bo'yicha 2018-2024-yillar real kuzatuv ma'lumotlariga tayanganligi bilan farqlanadi. Tadqiqotda tuproqning elektr o'tkazuvchanligi (EC) va asosiy meteorologik omillar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik ko'p omilli regressiya modeli orqali baholanib, natijalar GIS asosida fazoviy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari suv-meliorativ boshqaruvni takomillashtirish uchun ilmiy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi hamda kelgusida [6-8] adabiyotlarda keltirilgan matematik va sun'iy intellekt asosidagi modellar bilan kengaytirilishi rejalashtirilgan.

Ma'lumotlar va tadqiqot usullari. Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasining Ellikqal'a tumani tanlandi. Ushbu hudud Orolbo'yi havzasida joylashgan bo'lib, tuproq sho'rlanishi va namlik tanqisligi eng keskin namoyon bo'ladigan mintaqalardan biridir. Keskin kontinental iqlim sharoitida yillik yog'in miqdorining bug'lanishdan ancha kam bo'lishi suv balansining buzilishiga olib keladi va sho'rlanish jarayonlarini kuchaytiradi. Natijada grunt suvlari sathining ko'tarilishi tuproqning ustki qatlamlarida tuzlar to'planishini jadallashtiradi. Ellikqal'a tumani sug'oriladigan dehqonchilikka ixtisoslashgan bo'lib, asosan paxta, g'alla va yem-xashak ekinlari yetishtiriladi.

So'nggi yillarda sho'rlanish darajasining oshishi, sug'orish infratuzilmasining eskirishi va suv resurslarining qisqarishi hududda qishloq xo'jaligi barqarorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Shu sababli sho'rlanish jarayonini ilmiy asosda monitoring qilish, uning iqlim omillari bilan bog'liqligini aniqlash va xavfli hududlarni fazoviy baholash dolzarb vazifa hisoblanadi. Mazkur tadqiqot O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 25-martdagi PQ-179-son qarorida belgilangan suv resurslaridan samarali foydalanish, yerlarning meliorativ holatini yaxshilash va raqamli monitoring tizimlarini joriy etish bo'yicha ustuvor vazifalarga mos holda amalga oshirildi.

Tadqiqot 2018-2024-yillar oralig'ida to'plangan meteorologik va tuproq sho'rlanishi ma'lumotlariga asoslandi. Meteorologik parametrlar - o'rtacha harorat, yog'in miqdori, nisbiy namlik, bug'lanish va shamol tezligi - NASA POWER, Copernicus ERA5 va UzHydromet ochiq ma'lumotlar bazalaridan olindi[9]. Barcha ma'lumotlar oylik vaqt qatorlariga keltirilib, o'zaro moslashtirildi hamda yetishmayotgan qiymatlar interpolatsiya usullari yordamida to'ldirildi.

Tuproq sho'rlanishi darajasi tuproqning elektr o'tkazuvchanligi (EC) ko'rsatkichi orqali baholandi. EC qiymatlari 2018 va 2024-yillarda o'tkazilgan dala va laboratoriya tadqiqotlari asosida aniqlanib, 0-30 sm chuqurlik oralig'i uchun standartlashtirildi. Qo'shimcha aniqlikni ta'minlash maqsadida SoilGrids va FAO ma'lumotlar bazalaridan olingan global sho'rlanish ko'rsatkichlari ham integratsiya qilindi.

Fazoviy tahlilni amalga oshirish uchun relyef, yer qoplami va sug'orish tarmoqlariga oid GIS qatlamlari ochiq geoma'lumotlar bazalaridan olinib, yagona koordinata tizimida qayta ishlanib, Ellikqal'a tumani chegaralari doirasida moslashtiriladi.

Ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash va tahlil bosqichlari. Tahlil ishlari ketma-ket bosqichlarda amalga oshirildi. Dastlab 2018-2024-yillar oralig'idagi asosiy meteorologik parametrlarning (harorat, yog'in va bug'lanish) vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarishi tahlil qilinib, chiziqli trendlar yordamida baholandi. Natijalar o'rganilgan davrda o'rtacha haroratning oshishi, yog'in miqdorining kamayishi hamda bug'lanish intensivligining kuchayganini

ko'rsatdi, bu esa namlik tanqisligini yuzaga keltirgan.

Keyingi bosqichda tuproq sho'rlanishini ifodalovchi elektr o'tkazuvchanlik (EC) ko'rsatkichi bilan asosiy meteorologik omillar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik Pearson va Spearman korrelyatsiya koeffitsientlari yordamida aniqlandi. Tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, harorat, bug'lanish va ET/P nisbati sho'rlanish jarayoniga eng sezgir determinantlar sifatida ajratildi.

Sho'rlanishning iqlimiy omillar bilan miqdoriy bog'liqligini baholash uchun ko'p omilli chiziqli regressiya (Multiple Linear Regression, MLR) modeli qo'llanildi va u quyidagi umumiy ko'rinishda ifodalanadi:

$$EC = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 T + \alpha_2 P + \alpha_3 ET + \alpha_4 + \varepsilon$$

bu yerda EC - tuproqning elektr o'tkazuvchanligi, T - o'rtacha harorat, P - yog'in miqdori, ET - bug'lanish, RH - nisbiy namlik, $\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_4$ - regressiya koeffitsientlari, ε - tasodifiy xatolik. Model aniqligi R^2 , RMSE, va MAE ko'rsatkichlari yordamida baholandi. Ushbu model sho'rlanishning asosiy iqlimiy determinantlariga sezgirligini aniqlash va bashorat asoslarini shakllantirishga xizmat qildi.

Fazoviy tahlil uchun ArcGIS va QGIS dasturlari qo'llanilib, 2018 va 2024-yillarga oid EC qiymatlari asosida fazoviy interpolatsiya amalga oshirildi. Interpolatsiya usullari sifatida Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) va Ordinary Kriging ishlatildi. Har ikki yil uchun EC xaritalari qurilib, o'zgarish farqi quyidagi formula bilan ifodalandi:

$$\Delta EC = EC_{2024} - EC_{2018}$$

Fazoviy tahlil natijasida sho'rlanish darajasi o'zgarayotgan hududlar aniqlanib, ularning tabiiy va sug'orish sharoitlari bilan bog'liqligi baholandi. Natijalar sho'rlanish jarayonining hudud bo'yicha notekis taqsimlanganini ko'rsatdi. GIS asosida yaratilgan xaritalar suv-meliorativ va agrotexnik qarorlarni asoslashda amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, taklif etilgan yondashuv kelgusida qo'shimcha ko'rsatkichlar va regressiya modellarini integratsiya qilish uchun metodik asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Natijalar va muhokama. Ellikqal'a tumani uchun 2018-2024-yillar oralig'ida oylik suv balansining asosiy komponentlari - AETI (haqiqiy bug'lanish va intersepsiya), RET (potensial bug'lanish ehtiyoji) va PCP (yog'in miqdori) - tahlil qilindi. Tahlil natijalari RET qiymati har yili iyun-avgust oylarida maksimal (300-320 mm/oy) darajaga yetadi, bu esa hududda suv tanqisligining kuchayishini bildiradi. AETI esa RETdan ancha past qiymatlarda (100-140 mm/oy) o'zgaradi, bu tuproq namligi cheklanganligini va namlik defitsiti mavjudligini 1-rasmda 2018-2024 yillarda Ellikqal'a tumanida suv balansi o'zgarishining dinamikasi ko'rsatilgan.

Grafikdan ko'rinadiki, har yili yoz oylarida $RET > AETI \gg PCP$ tengsizlik kuzatiladi, bu iqlimiy suv defitsiti ($\Delta ET \approx 200$ mm/oy) mavjudligini bildiradi. Mazkur nomutanosiblik, ayniqsa 2021 va 2023-yillarda kuchayib, bug'lanishning oshishi sho'rlanish jarayonini tezlashtirgan.

Sho'rlanish darajasining hozirgi holati (2024-yil holatiga ko'ra). Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi Sho'rlangan yerlar bo'yicha 2024-yilgi ma'lumotlar Ellikqal'a tumani uchun sho'rlanish darajasining yuqoriligini ko'rsatmoqda. Tuman bo'yicha jami 29 052 gektar sug'oriladigan maydonning 86.5% qismi turli darajada sho'rlangan.

Ellikqal'a hududi uchun 2018–2024 yillarda suv balansining (AETI–RET–PCP) o'zgarishi

AETI – ishlatilgan suv, RET – bug'lanish ehtiyoji, PCP – kirayotgan suv

1-rasm. 2018-2024-yillarda AETI, RET va PCP ning oylik o'zgarishi

1-jadval. 2024-yil holatiga ko'ra Ellikqal'a tumanida sho'rlangan yerlarning toifalar bo'yicha taqsimoti

Sho'rlanish toifasi	Maydon (ga)	Ulushi (%)
Kuchsiz sho'rlangan	11 520.3	37.7
O'rtacha sho'rlangan	10 349.1	33.5
Kuchli sho'rlangan	2 024.4	6.5
Juda kuchli sho'rlangan	1 111.8	3.8
Jami sho'rlangan yerlar	25 139.9	86.5

Fazoviy tahlil va GIS natijalari. 2018 va 2024-yillarga oid tuproq elektr o'tkazuvchanligi (EC) qiymatlari asosida fazoviy interpolatsiya IDW va Ordinary Kriging usullari yordamida amalga oshirildi[5]. Natijada sho'rlanish darajasining har ikki yil uchun hududiy taqsimoti xaritalar ko'rinishida aniqlandi.

2018-yilgi EC xaritasi tuman markaziy va shimoliy hududlarida sho'rlanish nisbatan pastligini, janubiy va g'arbiy qismlarda esa o'rtacha sho'rlanish zonalarini ko'rsatdi. 2024-yilga kelib, sho'rlanish darajasi tuman bo'ylab oshgani, ayniqsa Amudaryo o'zaniga yaqin pasttekisliklarda kuchli sho'rlanish zonalarini kengaygani aniqlandi.

$\Delta EC = EC_{2024} - EC_{2018}$ xaritasi sho'rlanish o'zgarishining fazoviy dinamikasini aks ettirdi. Natijalarga ko'ra, sho'rlanish ortgan maydonlar asosan janubiy va g'arbiy hududlarda joylashib, umumiy maydonning 64% ini tashkil etdi. Sho'rlanish kamaygan hududlar esa markaziy irrigatsiya tarmoqlari yaxshilangan zonalarda kuzatilib, 36% ni tashkil qildi. Bu holat bug'lanishning ortishi bilan birgalikda meliorativ tizimlar samaradorligi yetarli emasligini ko'rsatadi.

Regressiya modelining natijalari. Sho'rlanish va iqlimiy omillar o'rtasidagi miqdoriy bog'liqlikni baholash uchun ko'p omilli chiziqli regressiya (MLR) modeli qurildi, bunda EC bog'liq o'zgaruvchi, harorat, yog'in, bug'lanish va nisbiy namlik esa tushuntiruvchi omillar sifatida kiritildi.

$$EC = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 T + \alpha_2 P + \alpha_3 ET + \alpha_4 + \varepsilon$$

Natijada quyidagi asosiy koeffitsientlar va aniqlik ko'rsatkichlari olindi:

Таблица 1: 2-jadval. Regressiya koeffitsientlari

Parametr	Belgilanish	Koeffitsient	Ta'sir yo'nalishi
Harorat ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	a_1	+0.42	Musbat — harorat oshganda EC ortadi
Yog'in (mm)	a_2	-0.31	Manfiy — yog'in ortganda EC kamayadi
Bug'lanish (mm)	a_3	+0.56	Kuchli ijobiy — bug'lanish sho'rlanishni kuchaytiradi
Nisbiy namlik (%)	a_4	-0.18	Zaif manfiy — namlik oshsa EC pasayadi

Modelning aniqlik ko'rsatkichlari quyidagicha:

$$R^2 = 0.82, RMSE = 0.13, MAE = 0.09,$$

bu esa model 80% dan ortiq dispersiyani tushuntira olishini bildiradi. Bundan ko'rinadiki, Ellikqal'a tumanida sho'rlanish jarayoni asosan bug'lanish (ET) va harorat (T) bilan bog'liq, yog'in va nisbiy namlik esa sho'rlanishni pasaytiruvchi omil sifatida ishtirok etadi.

Muhokama va amaliy talqin. Olingan natijalar xalqaro tadqiqotlar bilan mos keladi[11]. Jumladan, yuqori harorat va past namlik sharoitida bug'lanishning kuchayishi sho'rlanish jarayonini tezlashtirishi avvalgi ishlarida ham qayd etilgan. PHREEQC asosidagi modellashtirish natijalari ham eritmalar harakati sho'rlanishga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatishini tasdiqlaydi. Ellikqal'a tumanida aniqlangan $AETI < RET$ holati suv balansining manfiy ekanini ko'rsatib, sho'rlanish jarayonining faollashishini izohlaydi. Bu sharoit hududda meliorativ boshqaruv choralarini kuchaytirish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. Olingan natijalar asosida quyidagi amaliy yo'nalishlar tavsiya etiladi: sug'orishda suvni tejovchi texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish, drenaaj tizimlarini takomillashtirish va raqamli monitoring bilan integratsiya qilish, shuningdek, GIS asosidagi xavf zonalari xaritalaridan agrotexnik qarorlar qabul qilishda foydalanish. Kelgusida sho'rlanish monitoringini sun'iy intellekt va masofaviy zondlash ma'lumotlari bilan kengaytirish maqsadga muvofiq.

Xulosa. 2018-2024-yillar oralig'ida olib borilgan tahlillar Ellikqal'a tumanida tuproq sho'rlanishi dinamikasining barqaror o'sish tendensiyasini ko'rsatdi. Sho'rlanishning ayniqsa g'arbiy va janubiy hududlarda kuchaygani aniqlanib, bu holat hududiy suv balansidagi nomutanosiblik bilan bog'liq ekanligi qayd etildi.

Natijalarga ko'ra, bug'lanish intensivligi (RET) va havo harorati (T) sho'rlanish jarayoniga eng katta ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi asosiy iqlimiy omillar hisoblanadi. GIS asosidagi fazoviy tahlil sho'rlanish xavfi yuqori bo'lgan zonalarni aniqlash imkonini berib, meliorativ tadbirlarni hududiy darajada rejalashtirish uchun ilmiy asos yaratdi.

Taklif etilgan yondashuv kelgusida tuproq namligi, vegetatsiya indeksleri va sun'iy intellekt asosidagi modellar bilan kengaytirilishi mumkin. Ushbu natijalar Ellikqal'a tumani va o'xshash iqlim sharoitidagi hududlarda suv resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish, sug'orish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish va sho'rlanish xavfini kamaytirishga xizmat qiladi.

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